

A Hybrid Intelligent System of Heart Disease Detection Using Machine Learning

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Abstract- Heart diseases is one of the greatest dangerous human illnesses in the world and this disease is affecting very critically. In these cases, the heart is very slow and not capable to blood feed the rest of the body. Therefore, early detection of the disease prevents the patient from worsening the crisis. The identification of this disease via old-style medical past has been measured as not dependable in several pieces. Neural Networks techniques are one of several data-mining logical implements that can be utilized into style detections to medical image. From the training it is observed that Hybrid-Intelligent System develops the accuracy rate for the heart disease detection scheme. The commonly utilized methods of Heart Disease detection and their complexities are summarized in this paper.

Keyword- RELIEF, Artificial Neural Network, Support Vector Machine, Hybrid Intelligent System, Cleveland Heart Disease, Heart Disease Detection, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heart Diseases stay the chief ratio of losses in the last three years. Lately the technology of machine learning methods to progress software for support doctors into creating decision in heart disease of the primary phase [1]. The analysis for heart disease be contingent on clinical and

pathological information [2]. At first, old-style exploration methods were utilized of the identification in HD, though, they were found difficult. Due to the non-availability for medical detecting gears and medical specialists specifically in un-developed states, analysis and treatment in HD are very difficult [3]. However, the precise and appropriate diagnosis of heart disease is very imperative to prevent the patient from more damage. Heart disease detection scheme can support medical-professionals with detecting it station based medical dataset for patients. In biomedical field the information mining shows a vital part of detection the diseases. With biomedical analysis, the material providing via the patients can contain fixed and consistent symptoms and signs specifically while the patients suffer since extra than one kind of diseases with the similar class. The physicians cannot able to identify it properly [4].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- **Shylaja S., Muralidharan R. [5]**, designed a system for heart-diseases classification. This proposed system consists of projecting study and passed out on UCI-HD data) utilizing SVM and ANN systems. The hybrid classifier “SVM-ANN” act much well from typical style of SVM-ANNs. The gotten accuracy of this method is (88. 54%). These result illustrations that SVM-ANNs is the greatest hybrid algorithms for analysis for HD.
- **Polaraju K. et al, [6]** proposed Prediction system for HD utilizing Several Regression Typical. This study is achieved utilizing training data contains from 3000-instances and 13-elements. These data-set is separated for 2 fragments that is (70%) into training and (30%) into testing. Based on the results, it is strong of the classification accuracy of Regression algorithm is well matched with others algorithm.
- **Seema S. et al, [7]** attentions on ways for forecast HD via mining of statistics covering into healthy record utilizing NB, DT, SVM and ANN. A comparative training is executed in 2 classifiers for extent the improved act into accurate system rate. This experimentation, SVM provides maximum ratio in accuracy of system.
- **Ashok k. D., [8]** suggested changed algorithms like NB, DT, KNN, SVM, Logistic Regression(LR) and ANN. The LR provides improved accuracy ratio matched with others.
- **Olaniyi , et al, [9]** suggested a system from three-phases typical built on the ANN-algorithms into analyze HD in angina and attained a classification-accuracy of 88.8%. Additionally, the suggested scheme could be simply utilized in healthy care information schemes.

III. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

It has been developing by the target of classify individuals by HD and healthy persons. The presentations in changed ML prognostic models of HD analysis with full information and selecting features were verified. Algorithm of Feature selection is Relief used into choice significant features, this algorithm to performance for the detections (ANN and SVM algorithms) was tested. Hybrid intelligent system of Heart Disease Detecting as show in figure (1). In this work, all of the research tools and methods background are deliberated in the next sections.

Figure 1: Hybrid Intelligent System of Heart Disease Detecting.

1- Dataset of Heart Disease

Cleveland Heart Disease(CHD) [10] is dataset measured utilized in analysis determination in this work. Through the scheming for CHD data here were (303instances) and 75attributes, but all available experimentations denote into utilizing a subgroup with 14 for this data. In this study, we achieved preprocessing stage into the dataset, only (6-samples) have been rejected due toward lost standards and value. In the last testers for (297- samples) and (13- features) data is port and with 1- output label. The output label has two- classes toward style the absence for HD and the attendance with HD. Dataset Information showed in table (1). Therefore, features mat rix (297 *13) for extracting features is made. The data-set matrix materials are known in table (2) [9].

TABLE 1
DATASET INFORMATION OF (CHD).

Data set characteristics	Multivariate
Attribute characteristics	Categorical, Integer, Real
Associated Tasks	Classification
Number of Instances	303
Number of attributes	75
Missing Value	yes

TABLE 2
CLEVELAND HEART DISEASE (CHD) DATASET IN 2016 [10].

S.no	Feature Name	Feature Code	Description
1	Age	AGE	Age in years
2	sex	SEX	Male=1,Female=0
3	chest pain	CPT	Atypical angina=1 Typical angina=2 Asymptomatic=3 Non-anginal pain=4
4	resting blood pressure	RBP	mm hg, hospitalized
5	serum cholesterol	SCH	In mg/dl
6	<i>fastingbloodsugar</i> > 120mg/dl	FBS	<i>fastingbloodsugar</i> > 120mg/dl (T=1) (F=0)
7	resting electrocardiographic	RES	Normal=0 ST T=1 Hypertrophy=2
8	maximum heart rate	MHR	—
9	exercise induced angina	EIA	yes=1 no=0
10	old peak=ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest	OPK	—
11	The slope of the Peak Exercise ST Segment	PES	Up Sloping=1 Flat=2 Down Sloping=3
12	number of major vessels (0–3) Colored by fluoroscopy	VCA	
13	thallium scan	THA	Normal=3 Fixed defect=6 Reversible defect=7
14	label	LB	Heart disease patient=1 Healthy=0

2. Pre-processing

The pre-processing stage for HD dataset necessary to good representation. Methods in pre-processing stages as per removing element or attributes lost values, Standard Scalar (SS), Min-Max Scalar have been applied to the dataset. The SS safeguards that each feature has in range between (0 and variance 1), taking very features into the equal coefficient. Also, in Min-Max Scalar moves the data analysis such that very features are between “0 & 1”. It lost values feature row is fair cancelled as of the dataset [11]. Very these data preprocessing methods were utilized in this work.

3. Feature Selection

After pre-processing stage, the selection for features is necessary in this stage. FS is a major phase in creating a detection typical. It workings via reducing in total of input vector in a detection, toward have good analytical and little calculation multifaceted simulations [12]. We have been utilized standard state in the art proposed FS algorithm in this work.

3.1. RELIEF

Its algorithm gives weights of each dataset features and efficient weights mechanically. This attributes having high-weight values must be a selection of, then low-weight will be waste. “Relief-KNN” algorithms method in control the weights for features are the similar [13]. Relief frequent done n random training tasters (R-k), without range replacement, and n is the parameter. Each k, (R-k) is the ‘target’ tester and weight (W) of the is reorganized [14]. The algorithm (1) is the Pseudo-code of Relief FS algorithm shows in next section.

3.2 Relief FS Algorithm

RELIEF Algorithm

Require: for each training instance set S , a vector of feature values and the
class value

$m \leftarrow$ number of training instances

$a \leftarrow$ number of features

Parameter: $n \leftarrow$ number of random training instances out of n used to update

W Initialize all feature weights $W[A] = 0.0$

For $k = 1$ to m do

 Randomly select a “target” instance R_k

 Find a nearest hit “ H ” and nearest miss (instances)

For $A = 1$ to a do

$W[A] = W[A] - \text{diff}(A, R_k, H)/m + \text{diff}(A, R_k, M)/m$

End for

End for

Return the weight vector W of feature scores that compute the quality of features.

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for Relief algorithm.

4. A Hybrid Intelligent System

To detection all heart diseases as well as classify it from well persons we will, machine learning classification system are utilized. Common classifier and their theoretic training are discoursed briefly in this study [13].

4.1 ANN-SVM Algorithms

In our proposed system, the mixture of ANN and SVM is utilized in detection and categorize the HD analyses in earlier step. This hybrid process is utilized initially for classify in normal one and cardiovascular data-set utilizing ANN algorithm, and before classify the heart-disease data into dissimilar phases via linear SVM kernel. In SVM classifier here will be a hyper flat among sets in data opinions by way of the conclusion limit. In this instance, there have 2 categorized of data of normal patients and HD patients are utilized through this ANN-SVM hybrid algorithm.

ANN is a mathematically typical that mixes neurons that pass messages and is a supervised machine learning algorithm [15]. ANN contains of three modules with inputs, outputs and transfer functions. In the network, the input items income exceptional values and weights, which are changed through the training method. The output of the ANN is intended of the identified class and the weight is computed again utilizing the error edge or boundary amid the output into predicted and actual class. ANN is calculated thru the combination neurons. This's dissimilar grouping for neurons of unlike constructions is just like multilayer perception [16].

SVM is a ML classifier which has been typically utilized in classification problems [12–14]. It utilized a max edge approach that transform for resolving some multifaceted quadratic programs problems. Because the high performance of SVM in classification process, many requests generally applied it [17].

4.2 System Performance Evaluation

In instruction for checked the system performance, many evaluation metrics of scheme performance were utilized in this study. We utilized confusion 2×2 matrix, each opinion in testing usual is expected in just one box and as there are 2 repose classes. Additionally, it offers two types of right prediction of the classifier and two kinds of classifier of incorrect prediction. The accuracy shows the overall performance of the detection system as follows [18]:

$$\text{System accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Sensitivity(S_n): it is the ratio of the recently classified heart patients to the total number of heart patients. The S_n of the classifier for detecting positive instances is known as “true positive rate.” It can be written as follows [17]:

$$\text{Sn or positive rate} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Specificity(S_p): an analytic test is negative and the person is healthy and is mathematically written as follows [16]:

$$S_p = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This step includes discussions for detection system and products of dissimilar perspectives. In first step, we check the performance for hybrid ML algorithms as ANN and SVM, on Cleveland dataset of heart disease and full data features. In second step, we utilized feature selection algorithm on dataset as Relief to significant features-selection. In the last, presentations were check in features selected. Correspondingly, the k-fold cross-validation technique was utilized. In order to check the accuracy performance of algorithms performance assessment metrics were useful. All features were regularized and consistent beforehand relating for algorithm. All computations were done in R on Intel(R) Core i7 -2500CPU @4.10 GHz PC.

1. Result for FS by Relief Algorithm

This section selects significant features on by Relief algorithm from base from features weight. The greatest significant 6features were be selected via Relief are assumed. The rank on which the features are selected is displayed in Figure (2). Giving into the results, the greatest significant features of the analysis for HD are THA and EIA. We achieved tests of dissimilar statistics to FS but the acts of classifiers of (6-features) were very good that we only stated the act of classifiers for (6-features) in our simulation results. Also, only six significant data and reports are tabulated in this work. Table (3) shows the significant FS.

TABLE 3
FS BY RELIEF ALGORITHM AND THEIR RANKING.

Order	Feature	Feature name	Feature code	Scores
1	13	Thallium scan	THA	0.247
2	9	Exercise-induced angina	EIA	0.227
3	3	Type of chest pain	CPT	0.217
4	11	Slope of the peak exercise ST segment	PES	0.131
5	12	Number of major vessels (0-3) colored by fluoroscopy	VCA	0.128
6	8	Maximum heart rate	MHR	0.123

Figure 2: Significant FS by Relief Algorithm.

2. SVM-ANN Results

Based on the results and analysis of information, it obviously illustrates that the (ANN-SVM Hybrid) has greater accuracy compared with the other algorithms. The table (4) illustrates the study for algorithms measured into the detection of HD patient based on the specificity, sensitivity and accuracy. During testing process with different data-set, the (ANN -SVM) offers upper sensitivity and specificity compared with other algorithms. In figure (3) the performance the algorithm over the detection for HD is shown.

figure (3): performance the algorithm over the detection System.

TABLE 4
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MACHINE LEARNING.

<i>Algorithms</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Sensitivity</i>	<i>Specificity</i>
<i>ANN</i>	90.66%	90.40%	81.72 %
<i>SVM</i>	92.50%	88.6 %	86.55%
<i>ANN-SVM</i>	96.80%	94.30%	92.84%

3. Compared to Other Works [5]

In this section, compared results with Shylaja S. and Muralidharan R. [5] as shown in the following table (5).

TABLE 5
COPPARD OUR INTELLIGENT SYSTEM RESULTS WITH [5].

<i>Steps</i>	<i>Our System</i>	<i>Other System [M]</i>
<i>1- Data set</i>	Cleveland's heart disease	Cleveland's heart disease
<i>2- Algorithms</i>	1- ANN 2- SVM 3- ANN-SVM Hybrid	1- RIPPER 2- Decision Tree 3- ANN 4- SVM 5- Naive Bayes 6- SVM-ANN Hybrid
<i>3- Result (Accuracy)</i>	1- 90.66% 2- 92.50% 3- 96.80%	1- 85.30% 2- 86.12% 3- 81.08% 4- 79.05% 5- 82.97% 6- 88.54%

V. CONCLUSION

The paper discovers the hybrid of (ANN-SVM) as per the finest binary classification scheme aimed at detecting for HDs. Best of the HDs are incurable through its nature and these diseases style risky complications as heart attacks and deaths. Our (ANN-SVM) Hybrid Classifier method provides upper accuracy ratio of about 96.80% than earlier proposed technique. The result of this study shows that this hybrid ANN-SVM is extra fixed than the single Machine Learning process. This hybrid classifier is suggestive of that it is exact active of classification in that patients having or not having heart-disease.

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